

**EFFECT OF ASHWAGANDHADI LEPA IN THE MANAGEMENT OF PARIKARTIKA
W.S.R FISSURE IN ANO: A CASE STUDY*****¹Dr. Arpit Surya, ²Dr. Jayaram Anumarlapudi, ³Dr. Ramya R.**¹PG Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, ²Professor & HOD, Department of Shalya Tantra, ³Professor, Department of Shalya Tantra. Ramakrishna Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Bangalore, Karnataka.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Arpit Surya**PG Scholar, Department of Shalya Tantra, Department of Shalya Tantra. Ramakrishna Ayurvedic Medical College & Hospital, Bangalore, Karnataka. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18430546>**How to cite this Article:** *¹Dr. Arpit Surya, ²Dr. Jayaram Anumarlapudi, ³Dr. Ramya R. (2026). Effect Of Ashwagandhadi Lepa In The Management Of Parikartika W.S.R Fissure In Ano: A Case Study. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(2), 264–267.

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Article Received on 21/12/2025

Article Revised on 12/01/2026

Article Published on 01/02/2026

ABSTRACT

Parikartika, a painful ano-rectal disorder described in Ayurvedic texts, is considered a *Vyapat* (complication) of procedures such as *Virechana* and *Basti karma*. Its clinical features—sharp anal pain, defecation-associated discomfort, sphincter spasm, bleeding, and burning sensation closely resemble fissure-in-ano in modern medicine. Conventional management includes analgesics, bulk laxatives, topical ointments, dietary modifications, and surgical interventions such as lateral sphincterotomy and fissurectomy. Ayurveda, however, offers cost-effective alternatives with promising outcomes, including *Kashaya*, *varti*, *basti* therapies, *lepa kalpana*, and *sheeta ambu parisheka*. This study evaluates the local efficacy of *Ashwagandhadi lepa* in managing *Parikartika*. The patient had history of *parikartika* during pregnancy which was treated earlier, but now it had re-occurred. By the end of treatment, the patient demonstrated significant symptomatic relief and was cured. Thus, *Ashwagandhadi lepa* proved to be an effective Ayurvedic intervention for *Parikartika*.

KEYWORDS: *Parikartika*, Fissure-in-ano, *Ashwagandhadi lepa*, Ayurvedic proctology, Ano-rectal disorders.**INTRODUCTION**

Ayurveda, the ancient Indian science of life, emphasizes both the preservation of health and the treatment of disease, as reflected in the dictum “*Swasthasya Swasthya Rakshanam, Aturasya Vikar Prashmanam.*” Its therapeutic principles, including *Pathya–Apathya* and *Rasayana Tantra*, continue to hold relevance in modern times, though their efficacy requires validation through systematic research.

Lifestyle changes such as fast-food consumption, sedentary habits, stress, and tobacco use have contributed to the rising incidence of ano-rectal disorders, notably fissure-in-ano, haemorrhoids, and fistula-in-ano. Among these, fissure-in-ano is the most common and debilitating, with a prevalence of approximately 10-15%^[1] in India. It manifests as a longitudinal tear in the anoderm, typically at the posterior midline, causing severe pain, bleeding, and sphincter spasm. Acute fissures may progress to chronic forms if untreated.

In Ayurvedic texts, *Parikartika* is described as a symptom rather than a disease, characterized by cutting pain^[2] around the anal region. It is mentioned as a *Vyapat* in procedures like *Basti*^[3] and *Virechana*^[4], and also as *Garbhini Vyapat*^[5] in *Kashyapa Samhita*. Clinically, its features closely resemble fissure-in-ano.

Modern management includes laxatives, analgesics, topical anaesthetics, and surgical interventions such as sphincterotomy. Ayurveda, however, advocates therapies aimed at pacifying *Vata* and *Pitta*, including *Basti*, *Parisheka*, and local application of medicated *Ghrita* and *Lepa*.^[6] *Ashwagandhadi Lepa*^[7] is described as “*Param Vrana Ropanam*” for ulcers.

CASE REPORT

A 31-year-old female, married, software engineer by Profession presented with complaints of *Gudagata Shoola* (severe excruciating pain in the Anal region), *Gudagata Daha* (burning sensation at anal region), *Gudagata Raktasrava* (stools streaked with blood), Itching at anal region (Pruritus) since 3 days at Shalya

Tantra OPD of RAMC Hospital, Yelahanka Bangalore. Interrogations revealed that the patient used some local application in the form of ointment but did not get any relief and approached here for better management. The patient had history of habitual constipation and is not a known case of Diabetes mellitus, Hypertension or underwent any surgery. On physical examination pulse rate was 86/min, regular with normal volume. Blood pressure was 110/80 mmHg. All the laboratory investigations done were within normal limit.

Systemic Examination

- Cardio Vascular System - S1 S2 heard, no any added sounds
- Central Nervous System - conscious, oriented
- Respiratory System - Bilateral air entry clear
- Per Abdomen - soft, non-tender

Local Examination

- Inspection- Active bleeding was seen as the anal canal was visualized. On separation of anal verge, a longitudinal tear extending from the anal verge was seen at 6 o'clock position 1.5 cm inside the anus on the Posterior midline.
- Palpation- Tenderness present over the Fissure area and Digital rectal examination was not done as patient had severe pain due to sphincteric spasm.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Assessment Criteria

1.	<i>Gudagata Daha</i> (burning sensation at anal verge)
2.	<i>Gudagata shoola</i> (cutting pain)
3.	<i>Gudagata Rakta Srava</i> (bleeding)
4.	Pruritus
5.	Sphincter spasm
6.	Anal ulcer

Treatment Plan

<i>Sthanika Chikitsa</i>	<i>Samanya Chikitsa (Oral medication)</i>
<i>Ashwagandhadi Lepa</i> for 15 days	<i>Triphala Guggulu</i> bd for 15 days
<i>Avagaha Sweda</i> with <i>Sukhoshna Jala</i>	<i>Triphala Choorna</i> with luke warm water at bed time for 15 days
<i>Pathya</i> : Rich fiber diet. Increased fluid intake	

Treatment Course in Hospital

Treatment	Day	Observation					
		<i>Daha</i> (Burning sensation)	<i>Shoola</i> (Pain)	<i>Rakta Srava</i> (Stools streaked with blood)	Pruritus	Sphincter Spasm	Anal ulcer
<i>Ashwagandhadi Lepa</i>	0	++	+++	+	+	+++	+
	5 th	+	++	+	0	++	+
	10 th	+	++	0	0	+	+
	15 th	0	0	0	0	0	0

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Clinical examination of the patient revealed regression of symptoms with treatment by 5th day itself. There was improvement in all parameters, by 10th day there was

Nidana

- *Ahara* - *Ruksha Ahara Sevana*, *Amla Lavana Ahara*, *Madhyapaana*, *Guru Ahara*
- *Vihara* - prolong standing, sleeping late night
- *Manasika* - *Chinta*, *Krodha* etc.

Samprapti

Parikartika (fissure-in-ano) develops when *Nidana* (causative factors) impairs *Agni* and causes *Agnimandya*, resulting in *Vata*-dominant *Pitta dushti*. The vitiated *Doshas* localize in the *Guda Pradesha* (anal region), leading to *Twak-Mamsa dushti* and dryness of the perianal skin, which gradually becomes prone to fissuring. This cracked skin manifests clinically as *Parikartika*. In addition, chronic or improperly managed conditions such as *Atisara* and *Grahani*, when aggravated by continued indulgence in faulty dietary habits (*Aharaja Nidana*), further distort the anorectal structures (*Guda Vikriti*), thereby predisposing to *Parikartika*.

Diagnosis

Parikartika – Fissure in Ano (Posterior)

significant improvement seen in *Daha*, *Shoola* and Sphincter Spasm. *Rakta Srava* and Pruritus were completely resolved by 10th Day. On last day of treatment patient had no symptoms and was completely cured.

BEFORE TREATMENT

AFTER TREATMENT

DISCUSSION

The Patient Got Relieved of the symptoms and was cured with *Ashwagandhadi lepa*.

Probable Mode of Action

Ashwagandhadi Lepa is made up of *Ashwagandha* (*Withania somnifera*), *Durva* (*Cynodon dactylon*), *Lodhra* (*Symplocos racemosa*), *Katphala* (*Myrica esculenta*), *Yashtimadhu* (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), *Manjishtha*

(*Rubia cordifolia*), *Dhatki Pushpa* (*Woodfordia fruticosa*). It has *Vata-Pitta shamak* properties. It has *vrana ropana* action, as it is mentioned to be “*PARAM VRANA ROPANAM*” in ayurvedic texts. Also, the seven drugs in this *lepa* are having properties like *Sheeta virya*, *Kashaya rasa pradhana* which promotes *stambhana* action, *Vata- Pitta shamak*, *Shoth-hara*, *Vrana-hara*, *Rakta prasadana*.

Triphala Choorna was given for *Vatanulomana* which relieved constipation

DRUG	BOTANICAL NAME	Rasa	Guna	Virya	Vipak
1. Ashwagandha	<i>Withania somnifera</i>	Katu, Tikta Kashaya	Snigdha, Laghu	Ushna	Katu
2. Durva	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	Madhura, Kashaya	Laghu	Sheeta	Madhura
3. Lodhra	<i>Symplocos racemosa</i>	Kashaya, Tikta	Laghu, Rooksha	Sheeta	Katu
4. Katphala	<i>Myrica esculenta</i>	Kashaya, Tikta, Katu	Laghu, Tikshna	Ushna	Katu
5. Yashtimadhu	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Madhura	Guru, Snigdha	Sheeta	Madhura
6. Manjishtha	<i>Rubia cordifolia</i>	Tikta, Kashaya, Madhura	Guru, Rooksha	Ushna	Katu
7. Dhatki pushpa	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i>	Kashaya	Laghu, Rooksha	Sheeta	Katu

CONCLUSION

In this Single case study, *Ashwagandhadi Lepa* demonstrated remarkable therapeutic benefits, providing early relief from both cardinal and associated symptoms while also promoting rapid ulcer healing. These encouraging outcomes suggest its significant role in the management of fissure-in-ano. However, to establish its

efficacy more conclusively, larger patient studies and comprehensive clinical research are required.

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